

THE FEATURES OF TEACHING COMMUNICATIVE ENGLISH GRAMMAR ON THE BASIS OF DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS

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Abstract

This article is focus on the features of teaching communicative English grammar on the basis of developing professional competence of students, methodological analysis of teaching active and passive grammar in English, the ways of teaching English communicative grammar.

Keywords: teaching communicative grammar, types of active and passive grammar, methodological selection of English grammar, stages of teaching grammar (presentation, exercise and usage)

Introduction

The global socio-economic changes taking place in the world, the process of integration requires the development of the system of teaching foreign languages as a priority in higher education. In English classes, special attention is paid to the development of students' grammatical competence based on a communicative approach, to the use of modern pedagogical and information technologies in English language teaching. In the studies, it is specially recognized that the development of grammatical competence of students in non-philological areas of the higher education institution in a foreign language, in particular, in English, based on a communicative approach, is of scientific and methodological importance.

The issue of teaching English grammar based on a communicative approach is one of the urgent issues in the development of professional competence of students in non-philological fields. It is known that special research studies have been carried out on the role of grammar in language learning and the leading role it plays in speech communication.

Literature review

Problems related to the methodology of teaching foreign languages in various educational institutions in our country, the development of grammatical competence, which is considered a component of linguistic competence in English, its role and importance in language learning, as well as scientific and theoretical aspects of using a communicative approach in teaching English. issues were studied in the scientific works of the scientists of our republic J.J.Jalolov, L.T.Ahmedova, T.Q.Sattorov, H.T.Mustafayeva, M.Sh.Ruzmetova, M.A.Abdullayeva, A.A.Isakov, M.Kh.Gulyamova and F.M.Erkulova [1; 2; 4; 5; 6].

Various opinions and considerations are expressed in scientific sources on grammar, which is considered a component of language material. Grammar is defined as (1) the grammatical construction of language; (2) the science of grammatical construction of language; (3) there are those who consider practical grammar, i.e., grammatical rules for concrete language, description of grammatical events, grammatical skills and competences [3].

According to the German linguist G.Helbing, it is necessary to distinguish between three types of grammar: 1. A set of grammatical phenomena

characteristic of a particular language; 2. Scientific analysis of the set of grammatical rules in the language, i.e. the reflection of grammar in the science of linguistics; 3. The system of rules used during speech communication.

Professor J.J.Jalolov to grammar (1) the grammatical side of speech - the grammatical events occurring in speaking, listening, reading and writing; (2) defined linguistic phenomena as abstractions [3: 149-170].

Research methodology

If we look at the history of foreign language teaching methodology, we can observe that grammar has been treated differently. Proponents of the grammar-translation method understood learning a foreign language as mastering grammar. In the correct method, the teaching of grammatical rules is completely rejected. Proponents of this method tried to establish a direct connection (association) between the foreign language word and the subject, bypassing the mother tongue during teaching. Proponents of the conscious-comparative method paid serious attention to teaching grammar. Grammar is studied as a separate aspect. Grammatical rules are studied systematically. Currently, grammar is considered as a tool for speech communication. Researchers such as psychologists and psycholinguists B.V.Belyayev, A.A.Artemov, I.A.Zimnyaya, A.A.Leontyev, T.V.Ryabova pay attention to the formation of speech, its grammatical construction and recognition of grammatical events in perception [3].

In non-philological areas, it is required to master the grammatical phenomena of the English language in a functional way (from the point of view of application), and then apply it intuitively. One of the features of teaching English grammar in non-philological directions is that it is based on the knowledge learned from the grammar of the Uzbek (native) language. Grammar in the Uzbek language is taught after practical mastery of the language, and in most cases it consists of a mixture of theoretical and practical grammar [6].

Grammatical information in English language education has a practical nature in the literal sense. Teaching grammar in non-philological directions is mainly limited to the following: (1) mastering grammatical structure, their meaning (semantic) and usage (usage); (2) to know the rules of these forms, acquire the skills to use them in the communication

situation and context; (3) be able to use grammatical skills when expressing an opinion orally and in writing.

Students in non-philological areas learn the content of teaching English grammar. Teaching grammar, like lexis, is carried out in two stages: methodical preparation (selection, distribution, classification and presentation) and formation of grammatical skills.

The formation, meaning and use of a grammatical event is a separate grammatical unit. The concepts of micro-application, micro-meaning and micro-form are also explored in science [3]. The grammar minimum that students need to learn is given in the qualification requirements and educational programs of non-philological majors of higher educational institutions.

In non-philological areas, the main attention is paid to English grammatical phenomena used in professional texts in connection with the professional training of students.

Results and discussion

In the methodology of foreign language teaching, as in the lexicon, active and passive grammatical minimums are selected. From the point of view of the meaning, use and construction of grammatical events, it is possible to classify them as follows: 1. Similar grammatical events in Uzbek and English languages (use of the present continuous verb in English and Uzbek languages); 2. Similar phenomena in Russian and English languages (use of the future indefinite tense (Future Indefinite)); 3. Phenomena where the meaning and scope of application do not match (the difference is obvious in the example of verb tenses); 3. English grammatical phenomena (articles, complex tense forms of the verb) that do not exist in the Uzbek language.

One of the most urgent issues in the field of grammar is the formation of grammatical skills. It is necessary to develop grammatical skills in students so that they can freely use grammatical events in speech activities. Grammatical skills mean actions that ensure the automatic use and recognition of morphological and syntactic phenomena in speech.

The development of grammatical skills goes through the stages of presentation, exercise, and usage. The presentation stage involves introducing a new grammatical unit (presenting it in a speech sample), explaining them when necessary, and performing the first grammatical actions. At the stage of performing exercises, attention is focused on forming grammatical skills. At the stage of using the grammatical phenomenon in speech activities, work is carried out on the transformation of grammatical skills into competence.

Inductive and deductive methods are used to present grammatical materials. In an inductive presentation, examples are given first, and then the rule is followed. In deductive, a rule (or speech pattern) is given, and then it is practiced in examples. When choosing one or another method, the following methodological factors are taken into account: (1) the nature of the grammatical phenomenon, the similarity of the form, the easy discovery of the meaning requires the use of the inductive method. For example, the existence of definite marks in the formation of the

comparative and accusative degrees of adjectives in English requires induction; (2) similarity requires induction, and difference requires deduction; (3) prior acquisition of one of the verb tenses is the basis for the next one, etc.; (4) microcosms of new phenomena can be studied in different ways. For example, the formation and meaning of verb tenses can be presented in induction, their use in deduction, or vice versa.

Finding out the similarities and differences between languages serves to increase students' knowledge level, develop memory and logical thinking, and raise their linguistic level.

Conclusion

Based on the above-mentioned opinions and considerations, the features of teaching English grammar in non-philological areas can be classified as follows:

1. Non-philological directions teaching grammar does not have the status of an educational goal in English language education. It acts as a tool for teaching speech activities and is not taught as a separate language aspect.

2. Grammatical events in English language education are not new for students. Students are required to master these events in a communicative way.

3. Active (reproductive) and passive (receptive) grammatical minimums are approached differently in English language teaching depending on the type of educational institution, that is, in non-philological areas. At this stage, special attention is paid to teaching the passive grammatical minimum in English language education.

4. In non-philological directions, the amount of theoretical information about grammar is extremely limited, and they are given in the form of rule-instruction and rule-generalization.

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